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FEATURES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF MODERN JOURNALISM IN MONGOLIA AND CURRENT ISSUES

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ОСОБЕННОСТИ РАЗВИТИЯ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ЖУРНАЛИСТИКИ В МОНГОЛИИ И АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ

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Abstract

In this article, the author discusses the origins and growth of free and independent journalism in Mongolia and the factors promoting and hindering its development as well as other relevant issues. The author concludes that trends observed in journalism across the world such as globalization, convergence, conglomeration, and collapse are influencing the development of journalism in contemporary Mongolia. As a result of these factors, new forms of journalism such as online press, investigative reporting, environmental journalism, and civic journalism are actively entering the scene of Mongolian journalism.

Аннотация

В этой статье автор рассматривает вопросы возникновения и развития независимой журналистики в Монголии и некоторые факторы, способствующие ее развитию, а также другие актуальные вопросы. Автор делает вывод о том, что тенденции, наблюдаемые в мировой журналистике, такие как глобализация, конвергенция, конгломерация и демассовизация, влияют на развитие и формирование современной монгольской журналистики. В результате этих факторов на практику монгольской журналистики активно внедряются новые формы журналистики, такие как онлайн-пресса, журналистские расследования, экологическая журналистика и гражданская журналистика и др.

Keywords: free press, democratic society, investigative journalism, citizen journalism, online journalism, pluralism, media management.

Ключевые слова: независимая пресса, демократическое общество, расследовательская журналистика, гражданская журналистика, онлайн журналистика, плюрализм, медиа менеджмент

More than a century has passed since the foundation stone of modern Mongolian journalism was laid on March 6, 1913 in Urga (now Ulaanbaatar) by the newspaper "Shine Tol khemeekh Bichig" ("New Mirror"). More than 70 years of this period have been spent in the communist era, and about 30 years in a democratic society. Mongolia's media, at any time, has overcome many difficulties, developed in line with modern society, established a system of mass media in the 1970s, and today is moving towards the development of a democratic free press. The cornerstone of independent journalism has been laid since 1990, and today the semi-free press of Mongolia is one among the 70 countries. In the 70 years of totalitarian society, communist journalism can be considered a significant achievement for Mongolia. This is because the world's largest countries, Russia and China, still have independent media, as can

be seen from studies by influential world organizations such as Freedom Forum and Freedom House.

The purpose of this article is to identify the features and current issues of development of Mongolian journalism after 1990, based on the current practical activities of the media, the results of the author's research in this area, specific examples and data.

The emergence of independent journalism in Mongolia was initially influenced by the following five factors:

- In the late 1980s, the effects of perestroika in the Soviet Union affected all sectors of Mongolian society, including the media, and the operation of the Press Control Center (Glavlit) was banned. In other words, censorship was abolished and journalists began to write freely.

- Since 1990, the democratic revolution has won - the social system has completely changed, moving away from a one-party system to a multi-party system.

- In 1992, a new Constitution was adopted guaranteeing freedom of speech and of the press. In short, for the first time, Mongolia fully recognized its pluralism and made it public.

- In accordance with the new Constitution, the Government of Mongolia adopted Resolution 267, which gave any citizen of this country the right to own and operate media.

- On August 26, 1998, the Ikh Khural (Parliament) of Mongolia adopted the Law on Freedom of Press, which took over all state-owned media from January 1, 1999 [6, pp. 254-255].

Under the influence of the above factors, Mongolian journalism has undergone significant changes in a short period of time in the following areas.

First, the media system has completely changed, all media outlets under the Communist Party have been taken over and new forms of press have emerged that focus on the age, gender, profession, and political views of informal organizations. Also new parties, individuals, readers, viewers, listeners and directions began to be observed. The media has become a real platform for pluralism and publicity. If before 1990 there were only 84 newspapers, magazines, more than 20 radios and televisions [4, p.457], in the mid-1990s the number of media outlets reached 2,500. Currently, there are about 500 media outlets, not including information websites [7, p.192-193]. This number is the highest for Mongolia, which has less than 1.5 million consumers.

Second, the content of periodicals, radio and television programs has changed, and the scope of the topic has expanded. Thousands of topics and issues that were previously beyond the reach of the media and that were strictly forbidden to write have become the focus of daily information. From the dark side of the history of Genghis Khan to the democratic revolution, from the "rare" months in the friendly relations between Mongolia and the Soviet Union, to bribery, environmental issues, corruption, drug addiction, corruption of high-ranking officials, politicians, businessmen, shortcomings in the rule of law and the armed forces, and all aspects of pre-prison life have been widely reported in the media. In short, the media has the opportunity to play a role in monitoring society. However, as the number of media outlets increased, so did the number of general subscribers and subscribers to the regular press. This has led to "yellow" street newspapers and magazines that have never been seen in Mongolian journalism. This process continues to this day.

Third, there have been some changes in the writing skills of journalists. The problem of same topic, ignorance to adherence to the genre, the former empty praises and the worship of the same standard are gradually moving away from the official records, and one was able to write freely on any topic, to fully express his views, thoughts, and sayings. However, in the context of free writing, there are more and more "crazy man's notes", of one who writes in any way he wishes, whose materials are full of typographical and stylistic

errors, which are no more than a diary of an ordinary reader, which attract a lot of criticisms and ridicule from ordinary readers. Problems such as these have had a negative impact on the professionalism and reputation of journalism, and public confidence in the media has plummeted. In short, the level of writing skills of Mongolian journalists today is much lower than it was in the 1990s.

Fourth, there have been significant changes in the genre of media materials, methods and forms of delivery to consumers. The task of providing the mass media with information has increased, and due to the intensification of competition between the media, the information genres have become more important, and the genres of fiction and satire have decreased. Special issues, critical articles, critical programs of radio and television, programs were increased by 4.5 times in 5 years due to the proliferation of previously unspoken topics, and special attention to gaps and shortcomings [5, 138]. Some genres have disappeared, some have re-emerged, and some genres have become closer and closer to each other. It is a well-known trend not only in Mongolia but also in world journalism. There are also Western media outlets that produce "inverted-pyramid", "dramatic unity structure", "curve line" and so on. Such methods and forms have become part of the daily practice of the media. Although this is a good initiative, there are many shortcomings in the media genre. The sharp decline in the number of genres that require work, time, research, and talent from journalists such as essays, feuilletons, pamphlets, and reviews, rather than decline in just a few genres such as news, interviews, and reports, is a sign that journalists are abandoning difficult genres.

Fifth, in line with modern requirements, significant changes are taking place in the field of media management, in general management and marketing. The transfer of the ownership of all state-owned media outlets still had to be managed under the law of a market economy. Therefore, media outlets strive to learn about the achievements of world journalism in this area and gain experience in order to find their place in the competitive information market and work profitably. While major newspapers and magazines are strengthening their material bases and setting up their own publishing houses, all of them are implementing online models, publishing Sunday multi-page, small-format applications, advertising newspapers and running information websites. Also radio and television programs are broadcast online and began to operate two and three channels simultaneously.

Four main factors, which now determine the direction of development of the world journalism, such as *globalization*, *conglomeration*, *demassification*, and *convergence*, have a real impact on Mongolian journalism [2, p.130]. Next, let's take a brief look at how these factors affect Mongolian journalism.

- Today in Mongolia there is not only a steady increase in the number of media, but also new types of journalism such as online journalism, environmental journalism, investigative journalism, mobile journalism, citizen journalism, economic journalism, analytical journalism, cable television, shortwave radio

(FM), and media advertising etc. The direction and new tools have become real phenomena, and the public has the opportunity to receive information from anywhere in the world, to post their information, and to express their views freely through the social media. In short, information is no longer subject to space or time. To cite just an one example, today Mongolian viewers receive information in about 30 languages through about 200 cable television channels, read 201 periodicals (111 newspapers, 90 magazines, including 10 daily newspapers), watch 125 television programs (16 of them in our country), listen to broadcasts on 84 radio stations and receive information from more than 200 websites [1]. Since 2005, Channel 25 has broadcast more than 10 television programs, including TV5 and TV9, 24 hours a day, while other TV stations broadcast an average of 16-18 hours. The number of Internet users has increased 400 times compared to 2002 and now stands at 2.3 million. The number of mobile phone users has reached 5 million, with 165 mobile phones per 100 people, which is second only to Hong Kong (240), the United Arab Emirates (204), Montenegro (178) and Saudi Arabia (169). Mobile phone users spend more than 4.5 billion minutes a year on their phones [5]. Today, Mongolia is one of the most developed countries in the world in terms of the number of media and telephone users per 1,000 people. This is just one example of the "Global Village" which famous Canadian philosopher Marshall McLuhan predicted in the 1960s.

- In recent years, one of the most dynamic trends in the Mongolian media has been the consolidation of the media to a single power of one company. Today, 6-12 media outlets are consolidating into one company and the process of merging among the media is in full swing. A clear example of this is the fact that media companies such as Mongol News, Mongol Mass Media, Mass Media Group, Genco Group and Erkhjet Mongol Group own daily and weekly newspapers, magazines, news websites, television and shortwave radio stations. Just Mongolia's first media group, Mongol News, owns Channel 25, outside of its photo studio, a daily "Today", a weekly "Tavan Tsagirag" ("Five Rings"), "UB Post" (English), "Nyam garig" ("Sunday") newspapers, "Gereg" ("Deer"), "My Home" ("Our Home") magazines and "ABM" a publishing company. Some media companies have opened local branches and run two and three channels. The good side of this direction is that it does not need money because it is a large company, and the weak side is that the views of the company, its politicians, businessmen and authorities can become a platform for demand, and the balance of information is lost and the public is misguided. Such cases are often observed in the activities of modern media companies.

- Nowadays, as the choice of information consumers has significantly improved, the audience of the media is divided into many small groups, and the process of individualization by age, gender, profession, education, social status is in full swing. The development of online journalism has led to an annual decline in the number of regular readers. In particular, the number of young people reading newspapers and

magazines has decreased, and the main media they use has become the Internet and television entertainment programs. High-quality daily newspapers are mostly read by middle-aged, highly educated people, while weekly and ten-day newspapers are read by business people, local people and people with slightly lower levels of education. Bloggers are also finding their own readers and the number of users of their websites is growing day by day. The number of multi-page, illustrated magazines with modern design solutions is growing and attracting consumers of traditional media. 94% of the population of Mongolia listens to radio programs, 80% can watch television programs and there are 4-5 copies per reader including all copies of the regular press [7, p.112-113]. It is true that this is another significant indicator of the level of development of Mongolian journalism today.

- Another trend that has been evident in Mongolian journalism since the 2000s is that the information that one media outlet absorbs and disseminates from several other media outlets, and their activities that produce it, are becoming more similar. It is clear that the main factor that has a real impact on this is the new information technology and new media. As a result of the introduction of digital technology in journalism, the Internet alone is making extensive use of film and television animations, radio sound, photojournalism still image, all types of periodicals, e-books and the postal services. All newspapers and magazines going be modeled in online format, and radio and television programs are going to be broadcast via the Internet. As a result of this factor, the notion of information as category of space and time has disappeared, and its level of urgency and sufficiency has reached a new level. Along with the significant improvement in information capacity, the interactive capabilities of the media play an important role in the development of citizen journalism. Mass communications specialists predict that the above mentioned changes and the social system, the Internet is becoming a tool of everyday consumption and leading to new era of information consumers. In our opinion, this is directly related to the following factors.

The development of information technology has expanded the system of mass media coverage and improved access to the public to an unprecedented level.

- The concept of traditional journalism expands, its capacity and content has changed, journalism has become less of an individual activity and it has become an integral part of mass communication. Information has become a commodity, a business, and it is considered by many to be the main goal of the media.

- In the information market, a variety of media outlets coexists, and competition for readers became more intense.

- Social media has a real place in all spheres of public life, and some of the tasks of journalists will be performed by bloggers. The preparation of new information will be carried out not only by journalists, but also by any website owners, any citizens, and the role of journalists will be performed by ordinary people. The source of any new information has the

opportunity to be continued with the help of digital technology without a journalist.

- The speed of information has increased and is no longer subject to the factors of space and time. Due to globalization, the capacity of the majority of the public to receive information has significantly improved.

- Since Mongolia began to pursue multi-support open foreign policy, it has made it possible for the media to receive information in hundreds of channels in many foreign languages.

- With the development of society, people's intellectual, educational and cultural levels are constantly rising, leading to a different approach to the media.

- This requires a reconsideration of the mission and purpose of the media, methods of its work, its work in accordance with the requirements of a new era and a new readership.

- The media paid special attention to the issues of management and marketing, and in a market economy, the demand for information became the main issue. In short, journalism has become more and more adhering to the principle that "consumer is the king" in information market.

- Before 1990, party organizations and their leaders knew what to write in the media; however, today consumers will be able to determine it. At present, it is clear that any media outlet has no opportunity to work beyond the information needs of its readers.

- In a market economy, it is impossible to live without advertising, so there are private channels of newspapers, magazines, radio and television stations. Currently, 25-40% of daily newspapers contain advertisements [7, p. 197] is a witness to this fact.

- Over the past 15 years, the number of Mongolian media outlets has halved, and the merging of media outlets and the consolidation of several media outlets under the control of single person or single company depends on the consumer factor. On the other hand, this is the law of a market society.

- Currently, there are significant changes in the age and social structure of information consumers. While the number of readers of the regular editions has decreased and it is widely read by intellectuals and the elderly, the majority of consumers of television and websites are young people, and radio has become the main media of herders and farmers.

Despite such changes and good initiatives in modern Mongolian journalism, there are many problems that need to be addressed in the future. They can be divided into following five groups.

- 1.Improvement of the legislation on independent media, creation of a legal environment for the development of journalism, along with the transparency of state policy on journalism.

- 2.Formation of responsible, ethical journalism. Improvement of the work of non-governmental and professional organizations of journalists, strengthening the internal control of the editorial office and the control of journalists.

- 3.Taking the training in journalism, retraining, and professional development to a new level.

- 4.Establishing a private research organization to study journalism, developing a critical approach to the study of journalism, media activities and publications.

- 5.Improving the working environment of journalists and taking measures to address their social problems are topical issues in Mongolian journalism today.

Conclusion

- 1.Trends in the development of world journalism have had a significant impact on modern journalism in Mongolia, with significant changes in the media system, periodical publications, radio and television programs, the skills of journalists, and the media genre. This is a sign that Mongolian journalism is moving in the right direction, not lagging behind the development of independent democratic journalism in the world.

- 2.Mongolian journalism has taken a concrete step from libertarian journalism to responsible, ethical journalism. However, there are many unresolved issues.

- 3.Mongolian journalism has been adhering to the traditions of its development for more than a century and using it in conjunction with modern changes and innovations. This is especially evident in the periodical press.

- 4.Despite the number of media outlets, the search for and need for information of the majority of the population lags behind the modern world. Therefore, in order to move from quantity to quality, it is necessary to pursue a clear, targeted policy and take bold steps.

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